

THE RESEARCH OF SELF-REINFORCED HP SILICON NITRIDE

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SUMMARY: For the self reinforced HP Si_3N_4 ceramics the effects of $(\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{La}_2\text{O}_3)$ wt% and the ratio between Y_2O_3 and La_2O_3 on the mechanical properties and microstructure were studied. While $\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3 : \text{La}_2\text{O}_3 = 1 : 1$ (wt%) the flexure strengths and fracture toughness reach to a maximum at same time and the content of $(\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{La}_2\text{O}_3)$ approaches 20 wt% the flexure strength goes through a maximum 715 MPa (at 1350 °C), the content of $(\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{La}_2\text{O}_3)$ approaches 16 wt%, the fracture toughness goes through a maximum, 7.8 $\text{MPaM}^{1/2}$ (at room temperature). Analysis of toughening processes indicated that both crack deflection and β Si_3N_4 bridging or pullout mechanisms can contribute to the fracture toughness of HPSi₃N₄ ceramics.

KEYWORDS: self reinforce, silicon nitride, mechanical properties, microstructure

INTRODUCTION

Silicon nitride has the potential to become the material of choice for advanced application because of a combination of excellent mechanical and thermal properties. In general, fibers or whiskers are introduced to overcome the brittleness of unique ceramics, but there are several processing problems eliminating its application. For example, the component of different shape is difficult to well distributed. Selfreinforced silicon nitride or in situ toughened Si_3N_4 is based upon microstructural engineering through the controlled nucleation and growth of the $\beta\text{Si}_3\text{N}_4$ grains. During sintering, $\beta\text{Si}_3\text{N}_4$ grains with high aspect ratios were formed, therefore, the results are obtain similar to the Si_3N_4 toughened by fibers or whisker. Silicon nitride is a highly covalent material that requires the use of sintering additives to reach full densification. During sintering silica on the silicon nitride surface react with sintering additives to a glass. At high temperatures, the $\alpha\text{Si}_3\text{N}_4$ dissolves into the glass and precipitates in the form of β Si_3N_4 . The morphology of the $\beta\text{Si}_3\text{N}_4$ can vary from equiaxied to highly elongated grains depending on the characteristics of the oxynitrid glass as well as other factors such as Si_3N_4 powder, sintering additives, and processing condition. In this paper, the effects of Y_2O_3 and La_2O_3 sintering additives on the mechanical properties and microstructure of Selfreinforced HP silicon nitride are reviewed.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The characteristics of used Si_3N_4 powder are shown in Table 1. Sintering additives are Y_2O_3 and La_2O_3 , its pureness is 99.9%. The preparation process of Si_3N_4 ceramic parts are shown in Figure 1. The trial compositions (Si_3N_4 , Y_2O_3 and La_2O_3) were mixed. Mixing time was 24 h

in the polyethylene bottle with HPSN milling medium and pure ethanol as mixing fluid. After mixing, the ethanol was evaporated from the powder slurries. The powders were dried further in a air oven at 110 °C and then sieved through a 100 mesh stainless steel screen . Composite bars were obtained by hot pressing the mixture in a graphite die at 1780 °C, 25 MPa applied pressure in a nitrogen atmosphere, in 1 h. The initial experimental work of this study involved the determination of the content and ratio of sintering additives. For this, ten trial compositions were chosen Table 2. The composite blocks were loaded in three point bend at 1350 °C and room temperature at a constant displacement rate of 0.5 mm/min in air.

Table 1: Characteristics of Si_3N_4 raw power

$\alpha/(\alpha+\beta)$ %	Diameter μm	BET m^2/g	Impurity wt%			
			Fe	Al	Si	W
90	0.3	20	0.16	0.07	0.6	0.11

Fig. 1 Preparation process of Si_3N_4 ceramic parts

Fig. 2 Grain bridging or pull - out

Fig. 3 Crack deflecting

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Two toughening mechanisms are shown in Fig. 2, Fig. 3, grain bridging or pullout and crack deflecting. As this bridge zone develops, a closure stress is placed on the propagating crack that effectively increased the fracture resistance of the material. This increased fracture resistance is a result of crack bridging and pullout (Fig. 2). As the propagating crack collides with elongated grains, the crack would be deflected (Fig. 3). The extremely high fracture toughness is produced by an interaction between the propagating crack and the elongated grains in the material. Many investigators have demonstrated that the fracture toughness of Si_3N_4 is strongly dependent upon grains morphology. In materials containing elongated grains with high aspect ratios and large diameters, fracture toughness can reach higher values. Mitomo et al^[1] and Matsuhiro et al^[2] have shown that the fracture toughness of Si_3N_4 depends on the size and fraction of these elongated grains. Figure 4 summarizes the relationship

between fracture toughness and grain size for $Y_2O_3 - Al_2O_3 - Si_3N_4$ and $Y_2O_3 - MgO - Si_3N_4$ systems processed at different temperature. Figure 5 summarizes the relationship between the relative fracture toughness and the percentage of elongated grains.

Fig. 4: The relationship between fracture toughness and the diameter of elongated Si_3N_4 grain

Fig. 5: The relationship between the relative fracture toughness and the percentage of elongated Si_3N_4 grains

Fig. 6: $Y_2O_3 - La_2O_3$ binary diagram

The selection of sintering additives not only is a density criterion, but also is a key parameter in controlling the morphology of silicon nitride grains. The chemical composition of the glass determines the temperature and the rate of the α to β transformation. The glass composition also determines the rate of mass transport, which is directly related to the kinetics of grain growth. The effects of the ratio between Y_2O_3 and La_2O_3 on the HP Si_3N_4 mechanical properties are shown in Fig. 7, while $Y_2O_3 : La_2O_3 = 1 : 1$ (wt%), the flexure strengths and fracture toughness reach to a maximum at same time, flexure strength approaches 676 MPa (at 1350 °C), fracture toughness is $6.13 MPa.M^{1/2}$ (at room temperature). From Y_2O_3 and La_2O_3 binary diagram (Fig. 6), we know, while $Y_2O_3 : La_2O_3$ is close to 1 : 1, compound

(LaYO₃) was forming easy, sintering additives were at grain boundary in the compounds, not in glass, therefore, raising the softening temperature of glass and improving the Si₃N₄ mechanical properties.

Table 2: Effects of the content of (Y₂O₃ + La₂O₃) wt% and the ratio between Y₂O₃ and La₂O₃ on the HP Si₃N₄ mechanical properties

Composition (wt %)			Y ₂ O ₃ :La ₂ O ₃	σ_f^{RT} (MPa)	σ_f^{1350} (MPa)	K_{Ic}^{RT} (MPa.M ^{1/2})
Si ₃ N ₄	Y ₂ O ₃	La ₂ O ₃				
87	0	13	0 : 13	586.8	447.3	5.78
87	4	9	4 : 9	773.0	669.4	5.49
87	6.5	6.5	1 : 1	581.1	676.6	6.13
87	9	4	9 : 4	365.7	589.4	5.82
87	13	0	13 : 0	703.0	128.0	5.05
95	2.5	2.5	1 : 1	413.5	212.0	4.60
90	5	5	1 : 1	660.0	380.4	5.67
84	8	8	1 : 1	880.9	686.1	7.78
80	10	10	1 : 1	890.7	715.6	7.68
75	12.5	12.5	1 : 1	801.4	595.04	7.93

Fig. 7: The relationship between the ratio of sintering additives (Y₂O₃ : La₂O₃) and Si₃N₄ mechanical properties

The effects of the content of sintering additives (Y₂O₃ + La₂O₃) wt% on the HP Si₃N₄ mechanical properties and microstructure are shown in Fig. 8 and Fig. 9. While the content of sintering additives (Y₂O₃ + La₂O₃) approaches 16 wt%, the fracture toughness goes through a maximum, 7.8 MPa.M^{1/2} (at room temperature). While the content of sintering additives (Y₂O₃ + La₂O₃) approaches 20 wt%, the flexure strength goes through a maximum, 715 MPa (at 1350 °C). Fig. 9 is scanning electron micrographs of a self-reinforce Si₃N₄. Fig. 9 illustrates how the microstructure can be varied by the content of sintering additives when materials are made from the same starting powder and processed under identical conditions. In these materials, the grains with highest aspect ratios have been produced in the material containing 16-20 wt% (Y₂O₃ + La₂O₃) sintering additives. The materials made with 5 or 25 wt% sintering additives (Y₂O₃ + La₂O₃) contained mainly a large number of fine grains. These results clearly show that the grain morphology is strongly influenced by the content of sintering additives. The main benefit of controlling the formation of elongated grains is a dramatic improvement in the mechanical properties of silicon nitride. The improved fracture resistance and mechanical performance is the result of a reinforcing phenomenon from the whiskerlike grains, similar to the behavior observed in whisker-reinforced ceramics^[3].

Fig. 8: The relationship between the content of sintering additives ($Y_2O_3 + La_2O_3$) and HP Si_3N_4 mechanical properties

Fig. 9: SEM morphology of fracture surface of different content of sintering additives ($Y_2O_3 + La_2O_3$) for HP Si_3N_4

CONCLUSIONS

Toughening mechanisms of self-reinforced Si_3N_4 are crack bridging, grain pullout and crack deflecting. In materials containing elongated grains with high aspect ratios and large diameters, fracture toughness can reach higher values.

While $Y_2O_3 : La_2O_3$ close to 1 : 1, the compound ($LaYO_3$) was forming easy, therefore, the mechanical properties were improved. While $Y_2O_3 : La_2O_3 = 1 : 1$, the flexure strength of the

material made with 20 wt% ($Y_2O_3 + La_2O_3$) sintering additives goes through a maximum, 715 MPa (at 1350 °C), the fracture toughness of the material made with 16 wt% ($Y_2O_3 + La_2O_3$) reaches a maximum, 7.8 MPa.M^{1/2} (at room temperature).

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